

MAS Umwelttechnik und -management

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Impact of soil management on productivity and climate change resilience

**Processing data from the completed long-term field experiment
“Chaiblen FAL/FAT” for the software SoilManagerR, and
analysing data of four long-term field experiments**

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Declaration

I hereby declare that I have written this thesis on my own and that I have not used any other sources or aids than those indicated. I have clearly marked all passages in my work that are taken literally or analogously from other works as borrowed material, stating the source. This includes works from the internet. The same correspondingly applies to illustrations, tables, the use of AI and the like.

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Abstract

One of the primary challenges of our time is to feed a growing and more demanding world population with reduced external inputs and minimal environmental impacts, all under more variable and extreme climate conditions in the future. The conflict of purpose between maximizing yields and sustainable soil- and crop management is evident in degraded farmland soils and polluted groundwater. In Switzerland, the use of fertilizers and plant protection products is increasingly being restricted. This puts more focus on other yield building factors such as natural conditions (weather and soil quality) and soil management (cultivation, crop rotation).

The relationships between climate, soil characteristics and soil management, and their influence on yield and productivity is not yet fully understood. As a contribution for better understanding, data from the long-term field experiment (LtE) Chaiblen (TG, Switzerland) was screened and processed into comparable numeric soil management indicators with the SoilManageR package. These indicators together with other indicators relating to soils, yields and climate were compared with already available indicators from three other Agroscope long-term field experiments (Oberacker BE, Burgrain LU, FAST ZH). All the data was then assessed to find evidence of the impact of improved soil management on yield, productivity and climate change resilience. Soil management indicators aimed at improving soil quality were specified as lower tillage rate, more soil cover and higher carbon input. With linear mixed-effect models the effect of these indicators on yield, nitrogen use efficiency and yield in climatic extreme years were estimated.

The analyzed data showed that more soil cover has a significant positive effect on yields (=wheat yields, maize biomass and relative yields over all crops). In climatically extreme years the positive effect of soil cover is more pronounced. The analyzed data showed further, that more tillage up to a crop specific level has a positive effect on yields, but that the penalty of reduced tilling is less or even turns to a reward in warm and/or dry years. To maintain yields, methods for more soil cover should preferably be: leaving crop residues on the soil, altering crop rotations, introducing cover crops, applying organic amendments and an adequate but not the lowest possible tilling intensity, especially in cold and wet conditions.

The impact of more carbon input could not be assessed using the method applied due to various interrelations that could not be represented accurately in the explaining models. The assessment of the three soil improving management measures' impact on nitrogen fertilizer use efficiency (as a measure of productivity) did not produce any useful results because important information like nitrogen fixation and nitrogen stock in the soil were not included in the explaining model. The chosen definition of climatic extreme years led to an unbalanced representation of the four LtEs in the subsamples. To address these and other weaknesses of the approach and to generate more precise predictions about the impact of the soil management measures, suggestions for further investigation were made.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

One of the primary challenges of our time is to feed a growing and more demanding world population with reduced external inputs and minimal environmental impacts, all under more variable and extreme climate conditions in the future. Agricultural soils as the basis should ensure the safe production of food as well as ecosystem services, such as storing and filtering water, preserving biodiversity and contributing to climate regulation. The type of land use and specific soil management influences the physical, chemical and biological soil properties and plays a key role, both in degradation and in improving soil quality and performance.

There is a conflict of purpose between maximizing yields and sustainable soil- and crop management. Long-term field experiments (LtEs) show, that organic cropping systems with reduced fertilizer and plant protection inputs have lower yields but less climate impact and a larger biodiversity and provide a more fertile ground for agricultural production (Krause et al. 2024). Various other studies confirm, that not using plant protection products usually means lower yields (Möhring et al. 2021). An increased nitrogen input will mostly increase yields, as nitrogen is the base for amino acids and chlorophyll and therefore for growth. But it will also increase nitrogen losses to groundwater, and when the optimum amount is exceeded, the influence of nitrogen fertilization on yield decreases (Sinaj et al. 2017).

In Swiss agricultural areas nitrate exceeds the limit value of 25 mg/l in groundwater at almost 50% of the measuring stations. Degradation products ("metabolites") of pesticides exceed the limit value of 0.1 µg/l in groundwater nationwide at every third measuring station and so significantly impair groundwater quality, especially in the Swiss Plateau (BAFU 2024). Therefore, the use of fertilizers and plant protection products is increasingly being restricted. This puts more focus on the other yield building factors natural conditions (weather and soil quality) and soil management (cultivation, crop rotation). The question arises as to what extent soil management measures play a role in ensuring crop yields and climate change resilience, and in which ways soil management can be improved to compensate for coming restriction in the use of fertilizer and plant protection products.

To gain a better understanding of the relationships between soil characteristics, soil management and their influence on yield and the development of soil quality, data from long-term field experiments (LtEs) on cultivation systems are suitable. They show for example, that under Switzerland's moist cool climatic condition reduced soil tillage increased earthworm population, reduced infection of wheat, increased plant colonization by arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi and improved soil quality without substantial reductions in yield (Anken et al. 2004). Grassland experiments showed, that soil microbiome diversity and -network complexity positively influenced multiple ecosystems functioning related to nutrient cycling (Wagg et al. 2024). The soil biological activity is significantly promoted by a continuous and sufficient supply of organic matter as source of nutrients and soil cover as physical and climatic protection for soil organisms as long as it is not too much disturbed by intensive tillage at the wrong time (Weisskopf 1986).

Long-term experiments (LtEs) are usually carried out at one location, and they examine a few specific methods only. To investigate the influence of different soil management intensities and strategies under different pedo-climatic conditions on a broader scale, LtEs have to be analyzed together. The nominal soil management data must be converted into continuous, numerical soil management indicators in the sense of a common language of comparable and analyzable data for the various LtEs. In this way, the combination of the data of different locations and long

periods of time with different management strategies allows the use of new multivariate models to develop better and more site-specific recommendations on which soil management practice under which condition can improve yields, productivity and climate change resilience.

Agroscope has data from more than 20 long-term field experiments (LtE) spread across arable farming areas throughout Switzerland. The oldest of these experiments (ZOFE – Zurich Organic Fertilization Experiment) has been running since 1949 at the Reckenholz site in Zurich Affoltern. Around a third of these LtEs are completed.

1.2 Task definition and approach

One of these completed LtEs is LtE Chaiblen¹, which investigated the agronomic and economic effects of different crop rotations at different intensities. This data is to be made available for current issues and for joint analyses with other LtEs, which leads to following task definition:

- ⇒ Screening and processing the available soil-, plant-, management and climate data of the LtE Chaiblen FAL/FAT 1989 – 2000, so the data can be used for the SoilManageR package² to answer current issues,
- ⇒ Comparison and analysis of the processed data with already available data from three other LtEs to find evidence on which soil management practices under which conditions can improve yields, productivity and climate change resilience (= research question).

This requires the following approach:

- Screening the electronic and paper data for the LtE Chaiblen in the archive,
- Choosing and processing suitable data (experimental and climate),
- Calculating numeric soil management indicators with the SoilManageR package,
- Developing hypotheses on the research question as a basis for the analyses and the multivariate models,
- Analyzing the available data with descriptive-, correlation- and linear mixed-effects models on platform R to find evidence for the hypotheses in the available data.

¹ 1989 – 2000, FAL/FAT – see chapter 2.1

² See chapter 2.2

2 Basics

2.1 Longtime field experiment (LtE) Chaiblen

In the longtime field experiment “Chaiblen” the agronomic and economic effects of a versatile, a cereal-accented and a maize-accented crop rotation have been examined in the years from 1974 to 2000. The site “Chaible” is part of the Tänikon Research Station, Switzerland (FAT, today Agroscope) and is located 536 m above sea level. The precipitation amounts to 1'180 mm/year, the average annual temperature is 8.2 °C. The deep, gleyic, stone-poor and calcareous Cambisol consists of a clayey loam with a humus content of up to 5.5%. The soil is difficult to work and therefore corresponds to a marginal site for arable land use (Jossi et al. 2002). Table 1 gives an overview of the history of the LtE Chaiblen.

The first part of the longtime experiment 1970 – 1988 was organized by ETH and FAT and corresponds to the 1st to 3rd crop rotation period in Table 1. The focus was on different fertilizers and plant protection intensities for the three different crop rotations. The versatile and the cereal-accented crop rotations were cultivated in 12 replicates and the maize-accented crop rotation in 6 replicates, each with different fertilizer and herbicide treatments on a total of 30 trial plots.

From 1989 – 2000 a second LtE took place on the same site, which used the same plots and in doing so, continued the same crop rotations. This corresponds to the 4th and 5th crop rotation periods shown in Table 1. The focus was on the economic performance of the crop rotations in two intensities (integrated = IP / intensive = IS) and in four replicates each, which gives a total of 24 trial plots.

Table 1: History of the LtE Chaiblen (Jossi 2000)

year	Crop rotation periode	Responsible institution	*Crop rotations (CR)	Management	Fertilization	Herbicides
1970 - 73	Site selection, blind tests	ETH / FAT				
1974 - 78	1. CR-period	ETH / FAT	V, G, M		purely mineral and mineral/organic	Normal and double dosage
1979 - 83	2. CR-period					
1984 - 88	3. CR-period					
1989 - 90	Transition period	FAL / FAT				
1991 - 95	4. CR-period	FAL / FAT	V, G, M	Intensive (IS) and integrated (IP) **	G: purely mineral V, M: min./organic	Normal dosage
1996 - 00	5. CR-period					

*V= versatile, G = cereal-accented, M = maize-accented

**cereal integrated = extenso program

The **versatile crop rotation** corresponds to a mixed farm with crops and cattle, 40% of temporary ley in the crop rotation and mineral fertilization as well as organic (slurry).

The **cereal-accented crop** rotation corresponds to a farm without animals with 60% of cereals in the crop rotation and purely mineral fertilization.

The **maize-accented crop** rotation corresponds to a cattle fattening farm with 60% of silage maize in the crop rotation and mineral fertilization as well as organic (slurry).

In this thesis only the data of the 4th and 5th crop rotation period from 1989 – 2000 are processed. Table 2 gives an overview of the three different crop rotations in the years 1989-2000.

The picture on the cover shows the experimental facility Chaiblen in summer 1993 before the wheat harvest. The crops to be seen are potatoes (versatile crop rotation), wheat (cereal-

accented crop rotation) and silage maize (maize-accented crop rotation) in 4 integrated (IP) and 4 intensively (IS) farmed plots each.

Table 2: The tree crop rotations of LTE Chaiblen 1989-2000 (Jossi 2000)

Years	Versatile	Cereal-accented	Maize accented
1989*	Silage maize	Silage maize	Silage maize
1990*	Winter wheat	Winter wheat	Winter wheat
1991 / 1996	Temporary ley	Winter barley	Temporary ley
1992 / 1997	Temporary ley	Rapeseed	Silage maize
1993 / 1998	Potatoes/Rapeseed	Winter wheat	Silage maize
1994**/ 1999**	Silage maize	Silage maize	Silage maize
1995**/ 2000**	Winter wheat	Winter wheat	Winter wheat
Characteristic:	40% temporary ley	60% cereal	60% maize silage

*Transition period

**Sample years for comparative surveys of crop rotation effects on productivity and profitability

Figure 1 shows the experimental design of the LtE Chaiblen. Each plot has the size of 12m x 45m = 540 m². Three crop rotations with two intensities and four replicates make up for the 24 plots.

Figure 1: experimental design of the LTE Chaiblen FAL/FAT 1998-2000 (Jossi 2000) VIS / VIP = versatile intensive and integrated, GIS / GIP = cereal-accented intensive and integrated, MIS / MIP = maize-accented intensive and integrated

2.2 SoilManagerR package for R

The SoilManagerR package and its indicators allow quantitative and objective comparisons of soil and crop management strategies across diverse datasets and study types. It aims to facilitate the evaluation and monitoring of changes in agricultural management over space and time, offering valuable insights for farmers and policymakers (Heller et al. 2025).

Figure 2 shows as a graphical abstract how the SoilManagerR software calculates numerical indicators for soil management intensities from soil management information.

Figure 2 graphical abstract of how the SoilManagerR works (Heller et al. 2025)

2.2.1 Description of indicators

Table 3 shows the current indicators of the SoilManagerR. To facilitate comparisons across time and sites, the estimated carbon input, STIR values, soil cover days and nitrogen input are summed annually. These yearly sums are then averaged arithmetically for the period of interest, which is typically one full crop rotation or the period between two main crop harvests. The indicator “plant diversity” is calculated for the entire period of interest (Heller et al. 2025). As it is not yet defined in detail, it is not used in this thesis. Further indicators can be taken up on demand.

2.2.2 Management data and general data template.

The available data from field experiments must be analyzed, selected and processed into a given template, to compute the soil management indicators in a standardized manner. This template is part of the SoilManagerR package and includes a hierarchical three-level structure, classifying individual soil management events into six broad management categories (tillage, sowing, fertilization, irrigation, crop protection, harvest), associated operations and devices using a defined nomenclature. Together with the date of the field operation, an optional numerical value (tillage depth, kg N/ha, etc.) can be entered for a more precise calculation of the indicator (Heller et al. 2025).

In addition, yield data (quantity, quality, contents), soil data (texture, structure, chemistry, biology) and climate data (temperatures, precipitation, sunshine duration and radiation intensity) are recorded in a standardized way in general data templates.

Table 3: SoilManageR indicators, description, unit of measurement and range of values in the analyzed LTE dataset own presentation based on all data_per year and (Heller et al. 2025) and (Heller/Wittwer 2025)

Indicator	description	unit of measurement	Range of values/year*
Carbon input intensity	Carbon inputs by: ➤ Crops (root and exudates) and crop residues, estimation based on the crop yield ➤ Covercrops, estimation based on growth period ➤ organic amendments (slurry, manure, ...)	kg C / ha crop kg C / ha covercrop kg C / ha organic kg C / ha total	717 – 6'540 0 – 3'225 0 – 5'908 814 – 10'795
Soil tillage intensity rate (STIR)	For each tillage and sowing operation, a STIR value is calculated depending on the speed of the operation, the tillage type and depth and the share of the surface that is disturbed by the operation	Cumulated value ³	0 - 300
Soil cover intensity	Number of days per year or percentage of days between the harvest of two main crops with soil coverage by living plants and/or by residues of at least 30%	Soil cover days % soil cover % plant cover % residues cover	108–366 days 27 – 100 % 17 – 100 % 0 – 69 %
Nitrogen fertilization intensity	Total N input by mineral and organic fertilization	kg N / ha mineral kg N / ha organic kg N / ha total	0 - 280 0 - 703 0 - 703
Livestock intensity	Total number of livestock units <i>LSU</i> per ha with their manure and slurry applied (1 <i>LSU</i> is equal to a cow or to 105 kg organic N/year)	LSU / ha	0 – 6.69
Plant protection intensity	Number of pesticide applications (herbicide, fungicide, insecticide)	Number of treatments per year or crop	0 - 17
Plant diversity	Total number of sown species per crop rotation, plant diversity indicator (Tiemann) and Shannon Index (relative abundance of each species within a cropping sequence)	Not yet defined	

*Range of value for the analyzed LTEs, see chapter 3

2.3 Statistical data analyses

In this thesis, the following methods of statistical analyses are used:

- Descriptive analysis
- Correlation analysis
- Linear mixed-effect models

³ STIR = [(0.5 x speed in (km/h)/1.609) x (3.25 x tillage type) x depth in cm/2.54 x disturbed area in %], examples:

> plough, 20 cm deep with 8 km/h = (0.5 x 8/1.609) x (3.25 x 1) x 20 /2.54 x 100% = 63.6

> rotary_harrow, 10 cm deep with 6 km/h = (0.5 x 6/1.609) x (3.25 x 0.9) x 10/2.54 x 100% = 21.5

> classic drill, 6 cm deep with 8 km/h = (0.5 x 8/1.609) x (3.25 x 0.2275) x 6/2.54 x 65% = 2.8

> seedbed_combination,, 10 cm deep with 6 km/h = (0.5 x 6/1.609) x (3.25 x 0.5) x 10/2.54 x 100% = 11.9

2.3.1 Descriptive analysis

The aim of this analysis is to obtain an overview of the data and discover initial patterns. For this purpose, graphs and tables are generated in which the data and their calculated key figures such as minimum/maximum, mean, standard deviation, median 1st – 4th quartile and distribution are made visible and comprehensible.

2.3.2 Correlation analysis

The correlation analysis is used to examine whether there is a positive or negative linear relationship between two variables. The result consists of a correlation coefficient r with values from -1 (= perfect negative linear correlation) to 0 (= no linear correlation) to 1 (= perfect positive linear correlation). (Weber/Keller 2023).

The following guide values apply to the strength of the correlation coefficient r :

$0,0 < 0,1$	No correlation	$0,5 < 0,7$	High correlation
$0,1 < 0,3$	Low correlation	$0,7 < 1,0$	Very high correlation
$0,3 < 0,5$	Medium correlation		

The significance of the correlation coefficient is checked by using a t-test. The question is whether the correlation coefficient differs significantly from zero with a zero hypothesis, that there is no connection or no real correlation. If the calculated p-value is below 5%, it is assumed that there is a correlation between the variables in reality (DATAtab Team 2025). The p-value decreases by increasing sample size and degrees of freedom when the correlation coefficient remains the same. For degrees of freedom > 100 , correlation coefficients of $|r| > 0.2$ are usually significant (own calculation).

When a variable has to be explained by several independent variables, the information value of a correlation analysis is limited. To obtain a realistic estimate of the effect of each independent variable, their interactions have to be taken into account. For this purpose, multivariate models are suitable.

2.3.3 linear mixed-effect models

One type of multivariate models is the multiple linear regression analysis. It is used to create a linear model that describes the relationship between a dependent variable and several independent (explanatory) variables according to the following equation:

$$y = b_1 * x_1 + \dots + b_k * x_k + a + e$$

Whereas

y = dependent variable and $x_1/x_2/x_3/.../x_k$ = explanatory independent variables,

k = number of independent variables,

$b_1/b_2/b_3/.../b_k$ = regression coefficients = change in y due to $+1x$ (slope),

a = value of y when all the independent variables x are zero (intercept),

e = model error.

The aim is to estimate a dependent variable based on other independent variables with as little error as possible. Essential for reliable linear regressions is that the residuals are normally distributed and there is no high correlation between the independent explaining variables.

In linear mixed-effect models, random variables that cannot be influenced are also incorporated into the model, and their effect on the dependent variable is calculated as part of an additional

intercept. The multiple linear regression is to be completed with this additional intercept a_z (Keller 2024).

$$y = b_1 * x_1 + \dots + b_k * x_k + a + e + a_z$$

A restricted maximum likelihood estimation (REML) is used to fit the linear mixed-effect models and set the regression coefficients b . REML has the advantage that it produces less biased estimates of the variance components. (Maestrini/Hui/Welsh 2024).

The aim is to create a model that enables the most accurate possible forecast of the dependent variable with as few independent and random variables as possible.

To find out how well the regression model can explain the dependent variable, the following key figures are used:

$R^2 m$	marginal R^2 = share of variance explained by the independent variables
$R^2 c$	conditional R^2 = share of variance explained by the independent and the random variables
AIC	Akaike information criteria, measure of the fitting quality, estimates the amount of information lost by the model compared to reality, the lower the better, absolute value is not interpretable
df resid	Degrees of freedom residuum = number of data points – number of continuous explanatory variables – number of factor levels for factorial variables

(DATAtab Team 2025), (Hemmerich 2021)

3 Data analyses

For the statistical analyses the processed data of the LtEs listed in Table 4 were available. They represent a wide variety of different soil types, crop rotations and management philosophies.

Table 4: overview over the LtEs whose data is available for the analysis (own presentation, data agroscope)

LTE years	Location <i>coordinates (WGS 84) altitude, Temperature and, precipitation⁴</i>	Soil type <i>(clay/silt/sand %) % C organic⁵</i>	Crop rotations and treatments
Chaiblen 1989-2000	Tänikon TG 47.48121025 / 8.90403828 538 m.ü.M 8.7 °C, 1'189 mm	gleyic, calcaric Cambisol (41/37/22%) 2.69% Corg	3 five-year crop rotations, 2 treatments <i>Versatile + integriert/intensiv (Vip, Vis)</i> <i>Cereal focussed + integriert/intensiv (Gip, Gis)</i> <i>Corn focussed + integriert/intensiv (Mip, Mis)</i> (total 6 distinguished treatments)
Burgrain 1991-2008	Alberswil LU 47.14319732 / 7.999642362 530 m.ü.M 9.0 °C, 1'026 mm	gleyic Cambisol (29/19/52%) 2.14% Corg	1 Six-year crop rotation, 3 treatments <i>IP intensiv, IP extensiv/notill, organic (Bio)</i> (total 3 distinguished treatments)
Oberacker 1994-2022	Zollkofen BE 46.989608 / 7.461849 555 m.ü.M 9.0 °C, 1'043 mm	eutric Cambisol (18/22/60%) 1.54% Corg	1 Six-year crop rotation (without temp.lay), <i>2 treatments (tillage, no tillage),</i> <i>2 fertilizer systems (GRUD/Kinsey)</i> (total 4 distinguished treatments)
FAST I + II <i>(Farming System + Tillage Experiment)</i> 2009- today <i>(FAST I corresponds to FAST II but shifted by one year)</i>	Rümlang ZH 47.438889 / 8.527778 485 m.ü.M 9.4 °C, 1'059 mm	calcaric Cambisol sand loam (22/34/44%) 1.43% Corg	1 Six-year crop rotation (with temporary lay), <i>4 cropping systems (conventional+(no)tillage and organic+(reduced)tillage)</i> <i>4 subtreatments (with/without covercrop and norm/half N input)</i> (total 2 x 16 distinguished treatments)

This data is used to search for evidence of the extent to which soil management influences yields, productivity and climate resilience in arable farming (see chapter 1). The influence of soil management on soil quality (soil biology, chemistry, texture, structure and physics) will be investigated by another thesis (Förderer 2025).

Chaiblen and FAST are experiments for research only. The replicates of a crop and its treatment grow in the same year so that their yields have the same natural conditions and can be compared. Oberacker and Burgrain are experiments for research and education. The replicates of a crop and its treatment grow staggered so that each crop can be seen every year for demonstration purposes. In analyses that only look at certain years (see chapter 4.3), data is available for all crops at Oberacker and Burgrain. Chaiblen and FAST only provide data of the crops grown in these years.

An overview of the data and their patterns is gained as described in chapter 2.3.1. Then strongly correlating indicators are identified, and a decision is made as to which of the strongly correlated indicators will be used for the linear mixed-effect models. The correlation analyses also give an initial impression of which indicators behave similarly, oppositely or independently of each other. Finally, different linear mixed-effect models are generated and tested to find the one that gives the most accurate forecast of the effects of the independent variables according to the description

⁴ Temperature and precipitation in this table are calculated with the meteoschweiz data from 1971-2024. Therefore, the values do not correspond to those mentioned in chapter 2.1.

⁵ % C organic equals to approximately % humus /1.7 and corresponds to the average of all measurements during the trial period

in chapter 2.3.3.

The research question (see chapter 1.2) is specified as follows:

Research question 1: How does soil management influence yields and N-productivity.

Research question 2: How does soil management influence climate change resilience.

The corresponding hypotheses to be tested are justified as follows:

3.1 Influence of soil management on yields and N-productivity – hypothesis 1

As discussed in chapter 1.1, reduced tillage can increase soil microbiome and, in this way, improve soil quality without substantial reduction of yield. And soil biological activity is significantly promoted by the supply of organic matter and more soil cover. This suggests that improved soil management means less tillage, more carbon input and more soil cover. These three indicators deserve a closer consideration.

Tillage intensity:

Shallow or no tilling leads to more soil organic carbon in the upper 10 cm and less between 20-30 cm of the soil compared to plowed fields. The overall soil organic carbon from 0-40 cm remains the same (Hermle et al. 2008). A reduction in tillage intensity, whether in terms of intensity, depth or area, leads to an improvement in the soil structure on all soils, to more stable rainfall crusts and to improved infiltration of rainwater. The increased soil resting period helps the earthworms as the key shapers of the soil structure. (Joschko et al. 2024).

Carbon input intensity:

The first idea is that more carbon input leads to a higher humus and soil organic carbon content in the soil and thus to better soil fertility. But a higher humus content can also lead to lower yields (Kiener 2024). The connections and interactions are more complex than that.

Soil humus contents depend strongly on texture and are particularly driven by the clay content of the soil. The fine pores have a stabilizing effect on the finely dispersed humic substances because the soil microorganisms have no access to them. The total pore volume is increased linearly by the humus content of the soil. Humus content also enhances macro pore volume and thus the air and water flow in the soil through soil crumb formation. However, this effect is less pronounced and indicates, that the formation of soil crumbs is rather due to the stimulation of the soil fauna – e.g. through their nutrition via easily degradable organic substances. The supply of such organic matter to the soil plays an outstanding role in the stability of the soil crumbs and thus in soil fertility (Joschko et al. 2024).

Soil cover intensity:

Experiments show that uncovered soils are less able to absorb and retain water. On plant covered soils, surface runoff and soil washout due to heavy precipitation are significantly reduced (Liniger/Askrabic 2024). Cover crops are therefore recommended. However, the freshly tilled soil of the cover crop is very susceptible to silting. It might therefore make more sense to consistently mulch the crop residues after the main crop instead of sowing a cover crop and so avoid tillage. Mulching the soil surface with the remains of a crop protects the sensitive soil surface from silting up and promotes earthworm populations and thus the development of a favorable soil structure (Joschko et al. 2024).

Another point is that uncovered, plowed soil can become up to 60°C hot in summer. Even a dead mulch cover reduces the topsoil temperature to below 40°C. Living, green ground covers keep temperatures even lower and reduce heat stress for the soil fauna. It is assumed that extreme soil

temperatures and temperature fluctuations play an important underestimated role in the stability of the soil structure (Liniger/Askrabic 2024).

There is strong evidence in literature, that reduced tillage, more carbon input and more soil cover improve soil quality and -function. Whether this also leads to higher yields and N-productivity is the question to be answered. This results in the hypothesis for research question 1:

Hypothesis 1: improved soil management, which means lower tillage rate, more soil cover and higher carbon input leads to higher yields and higher N-productivity.

Soil management is measured by the SoilManageR indicators (see table 3).

Yield is measured by **yield** (in dry matter of main crop per ha) and **relative yield** (in % of GRUD reference). Due to big differences in yield dry matter between the different crops (see appendix 1), analyses that cover different crops use relative yield. Yield in dry matter is only used for analyses within one crop. These analyses are done with wheat and maize only, as these crops occur most frequently in the crop rotations and in all LtEs and there is sufficient data available.

N-productivity is measured by **AFE** (apparent fertilizer use efficiency = yield in kg per kg N-input) and **NUE** (N-use-efficiency = kg N-output per kg N-input).

Soil quality is measured by soil organic carbon in %, clay content in % and their ratio soil organic carbon/clay - an indicator for soil structure quality⁶.

3.2 Influence of soil management on climate change resilience – hypothesis 2

Agricultural plant production is highly dependent on climatic conditions. As a result of climate change, temperatures are rising, precipitation patterns are changing and the frequency of extreme events (e.g. dry spells and heatwaves) is expected to increase in the future (Agroscope 2025).

The effects of drought and heat stress on growth, development, physiological processes and ultimately the yield of crops depend on the intensity and duration of the stress factors and their timing during the growing season. For crops that produce seeds, the late vegetative phase before flowering, the flowering and the early seed set are the most sensitive phases to abiotic stress and largely determine the final yield loss (Wuyts et al. 2023).

Critical growth stages of cereals, including maize, occur in late spring and summer, when drought and heat can affect yield potential, final yield and quality. Nevertheless, there is no quantitative assessment of current yield and quality losses due to abiotic stress (Wuyts et al. 2023).

There are currently several agronomic practices to increase the resilience of cropping systems to drought and heat. Reduced tillage is already practiced to some extent in Switzerland and is mainly aimed at increasing the amount of soil organic matter near the surface. This means more nourishment for soil organisms as earthworms and has a positive effect on the water storage capacity of the soil by improving its physical structure (Wuyts et al. 2023).

In the light of these findings, the hypothesis for research question 2 is as follows:

⁶The ratio Corg/clay content of the soil can be used as criteria for soil structural quality. A ratio of > 1:8 suggests a very good structure quality, a ration of 1:10 suggests a medium soil structure quality, ratios below 1:10 suggest a high probability of poor structural state (Johannes et al. 2017)

Hypothesis 2: improved soil management, which means lower tillage rate, more soil cover and higher C input lead to smaller yield losses in climatic extreme years (exceptionally dry/warm and cold/wet springs and summers).

The climate data over the LtE periods is examined, focusing on temperature and precipitation in spring and summer. Mean yields in climatic extreme years are compared with mean yields over all the years per LtE treatment to find out which treatment deals best with the extreme conditions. Then the correlation analysis is again done, but with the data of the extreme years, to identify differences to normal years. Finally, the linear mixed-effect models are run with only the data of the extreme years to identify differences to normal years and to find evidence for hypothesis 2.

Climatic extreme springs and summers are defined as follows:

dry spring/summer = below the 15% quantile of precipitation
wet spring/summer = above the 15% quantile of precipitation
warm spring/summer = above the 10% quantile of temperature
cold spring/summer = below the 15% quantile of temperature

Only the upper 10% quantile of temperature is considered extreme, because temperatures have risen on average over the years (see appendix 3), and not all the later years should be considered extreme. This is a first attempt. For a sensitivity and further analysis, climate extreme can be defined differently.

4 Results

Table 5 gives an overview of all LtEs and treatments analyzed.

Table 5 overview of all the analyzed LtEs and treatments

LtE	Crop rotation ⁷	Main treatment	Sub treatment	name
Burgrain	KA-WW(ZF)-KM-SG-KW-KW from 2003: SM-WW-RA-WG-KW-KW	Bio IP extensiv IP intensiv		Burgrain_Bio Burgrain_IPe Burgrain_IPi
Chaiblen	WG-RA-WW-SM_WW KW-SM-SM-SM-WW KW-KW-KA/RA-SM-WW	Getreidebetont Maisbetont Vielseitig	integriert intensiv	Chaiblen_Getreidebetont_integriert Chaiblen_Getreidebetont_intensiv Chaiblen_Maisbetont_integriert Chaiblen_Maisbetont_intensiv Chaiblen_Vielseitig_integriert Chaiblen_Vielseitig_intensiv
FAST I + II*	WW-KM-AB-WW-KW-KW	Conventional+tillage Conventional+notillage Organic+tillage Organic+reduced tillage	With/without covercrop Norm/half N input	FAST_I_C_IT_mixture_half FAST_I_C_IT_mixture_norm FAST_I_C_IT_none_half FAST_I_C_IT_none_norm FAST_I_C_NT_mixture_half FAST_I_C_NT_mixture_norm FAST_I_C_NT_none_half FAST_I_C_NT_none_norm FAST_I_O_IT_mixture_half FAST_I_O_IT_mixture_norm FAST_I_O_IT_none_half FAST_I_O_IT_none_norm FAST_I_O_RT_mixture_half FAST_I_O_RT_mixture_norm FAST_I_O_RT_none_half FAST_I_O_RT_none_norm
Oberacker	ZR-WW-EE-WR-AB/SM-WG ZR-SM-EE-SW-AB/SO-WG **	Tillage No tillage	Fertilizer system: >GRUD >Kinsey	Oberacker_No-till_GRUD Oberacker_No-till_Kinsey Oberacker_Plough_GRUD Oberacker_Plough_Kinsey

*FAST II corresponds to FAST I, but delayed by one year, names corresponding to FAST_I_ ...

** 6-year crop rotation with variations (always without temporary ley)

4.1 Descriptive analysis of management and productivity indicators

Figure 3 shows boxplots of the SoilManageR indicators with their mean and standard deviation. *C-input-org* and *N-input-org* are similarly spread, as they are both calculated based on the applied slurry which corresponds to the number of livestock units (*LSU*), and no compost is applied. Indicators with lots of zero values have a standard deviation greater than the mean value. This applies for *C-input-covercrop*, *C-input-organic*, *STIR*, *N-input-organic*, *N-input-mineral* and *plant-protection*. Apart from *soil-cover-days* the median values of the indicators are relatively low and there are some outliers with very high values.

⁷ Abbreviations for the individual crops are explained appendix 1, table mean yield and relative yield by LtE and crop, page 38

Indicator	C_input	C_input_covercrop	C_input_organic	STIR	soil_cover_days	N_input	N_input_organic	N_input_mineral	Plant_protection
Mean	3'501 kg/ha	482 kg/ha	529 kg/ha	54.77	290 days	106 kg/ha	54 kg/ha	52 kg/ha	1.78 treatments
Standard deviation	1'815 kg/ha	943 kg/ha	844 kg/ha	64.44	66 days	73 kg/ha	82 kg/ha	54 kg/ha	2.53 treatments

Figure 3 SoilManagerR indicators, individual values per year for all plots and years

(all_data_per_year, 2'606 observations)

Figure 4 shows the SoilManagerR indicators by the 29 LtE treatments with their mean values per year for the whole experiment timeline. Each treatment has its own specific combination of the SoilManagerR indicators.

C-input (not shown) is the sum of *C-input-crop* + *C-input-CC* + *C-input-org*.

C-input-crop is high in Burgrain because of high yields and in Oberacker because of more crop residues.

C-input-CC is very high in Oberacker, medium in FAST with covercrops.

C-input-org is high with livestock farming and zero without, which corresponds to *N-input-org*.

N-input (not shown) is the sum of *N-input-org* and *N-input-min*. It is highest in intensive older treatments (Burgrain, Chaiblen) and lowest in norm treatments (Oberacker GRUD/Kinsey). FAST shows the differentiated methods of half and full standard fertilization.

N-input-min is zero in organic treatments and lower with higher **N-input-organic**.

STIR is lower than average in FAST no and reduced tillage and Oberacker no till

Soil-cover (in % this time) is lower than average with no temporary lay, no cover crop and normal tillage, the combination of cover crops with no tillage leads to highest soil cover.

Plant-protection treatments are zero in organic treatments and highest in intensive and conventional no till treatments.

These treatments cover a wide variety of different treatment combinations. Some of them are common in agricultural practice, others are mainly designed for research questions.

In appendix 1, the exact values of all the indicators are shown.

Figure 4 SoilManagerR indicators by the 29 LTE treatments – mean values per year (=black line) for the whole experiment timeline (all_data_per_year, 29 observations), FAST I + II are very similar. For a clearer presentation, the graph shows just FAST I

Figure 5 shows the yield and N-use efficiency indicators per Lte treatment.

Figure 5 mean yield, relative yield, AFE and NUE by the 29 Lte treatments – mean values per year for the whole experiment timeline (all_data_per_crop, 29 observations), FAST I + II are very similar, the graph shows just FAST I

More intensive treatments mostly show higher yields and partly lower N- and fertilizer use efficiency.

Burgrain has the highest yields and relative yields but low AFE (kg yield DM / kg N-input) and no value for NUE (kg N-output / kg N-input).

Chaiblen has high yields in maize focused crop rotations, and low yield in cereal focused crop rotations because maize yields are much higher and cereal yields are lower than the average crop. Relative yields are closer to the average line. AFE and NUE are below average.

FAST has below average yields and organic relative yields. Conventional relative yields are above average. The different *N-input* levels result in different relative yield levels. AFE and NUE are higher with half *N-input* and in conventional treatments and below average in organic treatments.

Oberacker has average yields and relative yields and a very high AFE, no value for NUE

In appendix 1 boxplots of the productivity indicators with their mean and standard deviation are shown, as well as tables with yields in t of dry matter per ha and relative yields in % of GRUD references. Yields dry matter vary from 2,25 t/ha (faba, spring) to 19.6 t/ha (maize, silage). It does only make sense to use them for analyses within one crop. For all the analyses that include several crops, relative yield is the indicator to be used.

4.2 Influence of soil management on yield and productivity

Strong correlations between possible indicators must be identified, to exclude strong dependencies of the explanatory (independent) variables in the linear mixed-effect models. This is done with a correlation analysis of the mean values per year for the different LtE treatments, because AFE and NUE can only be calculated, when *N-input* is > 0, which is not always the case with the individual values.

Figure 6 correlations between similar SoilManagerR and productivity indicators, mean values (all_data_per_crop), 29 observations

The data supports the theory described in 3.1. Soil organic content (*Corg*) depends highly on clay content of the soil (*clay*) with a correlation of 0.96. The indicators *clay* and with it *Corg* are strongly site-specific (see also table 4).

C-input-org and *N-input-org* are calculated based on *LSU*. Figure 6 shows a very high correlation in the data between the mean values of these three indicators (> 0.98, see also Figure 4).

NUE is not calculated for the LtEs Oberacker and Burgrain. Mean values for *AFE* are highly correlated with *NUE* (0.95) in Chaiblen and FAST data.

C-input-crop is calculated on the base of crop yield, and it contains both the roots and exudates of the harvested crop and the left crop residues. Crop residues vary depending on the crop and type of farming. Figure 6 shows just a medium positive correlation between *mean.relative-yield* and *mean C-input-crop* of 0.33.

4.2.1 Correlation analyses

For the following over all correlation analyses the indicators *clay*, *C-input-org* and *NUE* will be dropped. To be able to work with individual values instead of mean values per treatment, infinite values for *AFE* (see appendix 1) are replaced with the maximum value of 900 kg yield DM per kg N-input.

As explained in chapter 4.1, the correlation analysis over all crops is carried out with relative yield in %. The one with wheat uses yield dry matter. Maize for silage and maize for grain have very different yields in dry matter (see appendix 1). As they are to be analyzed together, their biomass dry matter is taken as a comparable variable instead of yield. The annual biomass dry matter of Burgrain maize stalks were estimated according to the relation found in the FAST LtE⁸ due to lack of this specific information in the dataset.

Table 6 shows a summary of the correlation coefficients $|r| > 0.1$ between management-, soil-, yield- and productivity indicators for all crops, all wheat crops and all maize crops based on the correlation matrices in appendix 2. The indicators of interest are highlighted in yellow.

Table 6 Summary correlation analyses based on correlation matrices shown in appendix 2, indicators of interest highlighted in gray

Coefficient	Positive correlation			Negative correlation		
	low 0.1-0.3	medium 0.3-0.5	high 0.5-1	low -(0.1-0.3)	medium -(0.3-0.5)	high -(0.5-1)
Response variable						
Relative-yield all crops	C_input_crop, STIR, N_input_min, plant_protection, C_to_clay			N_input_org		
Yield_DM_wheat	Soil_cover, Corg, C_to_clay	C_input_crop	N_input_min, Plant_protection			N_input_org
Biomass_DM maize	C_input_CC, soil_cover, N_input_min, Plant_protection	C_input_crop		STIR, N_input_org	Corg	
AFE all crops		C_input_crop		Corg	N_input_org, N_input_min	
AFE wheat	C_input_crop, Corg			N_input_org, N_input_min		
AFE maize	C_input_CC, Soil_cover, C_to_clay		N_input_min, Plant_protection		C_input_crop, STIR	N_input_org

⁸ Biomass_DM = 1.6126 t/ha + (1.91168 x crop_product), whereas crop_product = grain yield DM without stalk

The correlation analysis **supports** hypothesis 1 partly as follows:

- **C-input-crop** is low to medium positively correlated to all yield indicators. This is expected, as it is calculated as a function of the yield.
C-input-crop is low to medium positively correlated to AFE in the overall crops data and in the wheat crops.
- **C-input-CC** is low positively correlated with biomass-DM and AFE of all maize crops.
- **STIR** is low negatively correlated with biomass-DM of maize and medium negative correlated with AFE of the maize crops.
- **Soil-cover** is low positively correlated with wheat yield, biomass-DM and AFE of the maize crops.

The correlation analysis **contradicts** hypothesis 1 as follows:

- **C-input-crop** is medium negatively correlated with AFE in the maize crops.
- **C-input-org** which is represented here with the strongly correlated **N-input-org** is negatively correlated with all yield indicators. It is also highly negative correlated to plant-protection. This indicates that most of the treatments that apply organic C, are organic treatments with no or less plant-protection treatments and lower yields.
- **STIR** is low positively correlated with yield of overall crops

Plant-protection and *N-input-min* are, as expected, positively correlated with yield indicators, especially in wheat crops. *AFE* is correlated negatively with *N-input-min* except for maize. It seems, that the declining marginal utility of fertilizer appears earlier for wheat than for maize. *C-to-clay* ratio is correlated positively to yield all crops and wheat and to AFE in maize crops. *Corg* is positively correlated with yield and AFE for wheat, and negatively with biomass-DM maize and AFE all crops.

These results just show, which indicators behave in the same way, but no prediction about the impact of an indicator on yield and productivity can be made.

4.2.2 Linear mixed-effect model analyses

A valid linear mixed-effect model contains all variables with impact. For explaining yield and AFE best possible, management-, climate- and soil variables are needed as fixed effects. The search for the best linear mixed-effect model is based on following considerations:

- Indicator *C-input-crop* is not used as an independent variable because it is calculated on the base of the yield and moderately correlated with it. This could falsify the outcome.
- All the other indicators of the correlation analysis are used in the model.
- As climate indicators precipitation and temperatures in the spring months (March – May) for wheat and in summer (June – August) for maize are added as independent variables.
- Pre crop can influence yield and productivity. Tests with pre crop as an explaining variable in the model showed a slightly improved fitting of the model and some pre-crops with a significant effect. But the effects of the indicators of interest do not change significantly. In the smaller data sets used in chapter 4.3 with the climatically extreme years, not all the pre crops are included, which complicates interpretation. Therefore, pre-crop is not used as an explaining variable in the model.
- As random effects LtE-name/block-ID/treatment-ID⁹ and LtE-name:year¹⁰ show the best fit for the data, as this combination corresponds to the effective number of replicates.

⁹ Block and treatment are specific for each LtE and therefore nested, not all combinations occur

¹⁰ All the combinations of LtE and year occur and are of interest

- To compensate for different sample sizes per LtE, treatment and block, observations are weighted with $1/n$ whereas n is the number of observations.

This leads to the following linear mixed-effect model with all-data-wheat:

$$\text{annual_yied_mp_DM} * 1000 \sim \text{fixed effects } (C_input_CC + STIR + soil_cover + N_input_org + N_input_min + \text{plant_protection} + Corg + C_to_clay + Prec_spring + Temp_spring) + \text{random effects } (1|LtE_name/block_ID/treatment_ID) + (1|LtE_name:year)$$

The complete outcome is shown in appendix 3. The predicted effects of the four indicators of interest concerning hypothesis 1 is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 predicted effects of C_input_CC, STIR, soil_cover and N_input_org on annual_yield_mp_DM wheat and the real observations (all_data_wheat, blue line = linear prediction with confidence interval, yellow points = observations with fitted curve, annual_yield_mp_DM*1000 = wheat yield dry matter in kg/ha, N and C_input in kg/ha, soil cover in %, STIR see table 3)

C-input-covercrop and N(C)-input-org have a negative predicted effect on yield (blue line). The real observations show a maximum yield with about 800 kg C-input-covercrop and a positive effect of N(C)-input-org in the range between 120-200 kg N-input-org.

STIR and soil cover have a positive predicted effect on yield. The real observations show a maximum yield at a STIR value of about 85 and at a soil cover of about 78%.

The linear mixed-effect model with all-data-maize has as a dependent variable *total biomass dry matter* instead of *yield* for a better comparability of grain and silage maize. Because this does not settle all the differences, the independent variable *crop* was supplemented. The used model is as follows:

Annual_total_biomass_maincrop_DM * 1000 ~
fixed effects (C_input_CC + STIR + soil_cover + N_input_org + N_input_min + plant_protection + Corg + C_to_clay + Prec_summer + Temp_summer) +crop
random effects (1|LtE_name/block_ID/treatment_ID) + (1|LtE_name:year)

The complete outcome is shown in appendix 3. The predicted effect of the four indicators of interest concerning hypothesis 1 is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8 predicted effects of C_input_CC, STIR, soil_cover and N_input_org on annual_total_biomass_mainproduct_DM maize and the real observations (all_data_maize, blue line = linear prediction with confidence interval, yellow points = observations with fitted curve, annual_total_biomass_maincrop_DM*1000 = total maize biomass dry matter in kg/ha, N and C_input in kg/ha, soil cover in %, STIR see table 3)

C-input-covercrop has a slightly negative predicted effect and *N(C)-input-org* has a negative predicted effect on *total biomass DM*. The real observations fit quite well with this line.

STIR and *soil cover* have a positive predicted effect on *total biomass DM*. The real observations show a maximum *total biomass DM* at a *STIR* value of about 160 and at a *soil cover* of about 90%.

For the linear mixed-effect models with AFE as a dependent variable, datapoints with infinite AFE values are filtered out of the dataset. The model with all-data-wheat looks as follows:

$$AFE \sim \text{fixed effects } (C_input_CC + STIR + soil_cover + N_input_org + N_input_min + plant_protection + Corg + C_to_clay + Prec_spring + Temp_spring) \\ \text{random effects } (1|LtE_name/block_ID/treatment_ID) + (1|LtE_name:year)$$

The complete outcome is shown in appendix 3. The predicted effect of the four indicators of interest concerning hypothesis 1 is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 predicted effects of C_input_CC, STIR, soil_cover and N_input_org on AFE in all wheat crops and the real observations (*all_data_wheat*, blue line = linear prediction with confidence interval, yellow points = observations with fitted curve, AFE = kg yield dry matter/kg N_input, N and C_input in kg/ha, soil cover in %, STIR see table 3)

C-input-covercrop, STIR and soil cover have no predicted effect on AFE (blue line). The real observations show a maximum AFE with about 800 kg C-input-covercrop and some outliers with a very high AFE in the range of 80-100 STIR value and 60-70 % soil cover.

N(C)-input-org has a clearly negative predicted effect on AFE which flattens above about 80 kg N-input-org per ha.

The model with all-data-maize looks as follows:

AFE ~ **fixed effects** (C_input_CC + STIR + soil_cover + N_input_org + N_input_min + plant_protection + Corg + C_to_clay + Prec_summer + Temp_summer + crop)
random effects (1|LtE_name/block_ID/treatment_ID) + (1|LtE_name:year)

The complete outcome is shown in appendix 3. The predicted effect of the four indicators of interest concerning hypothesis 1 is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 predicted effects of C_input_CC, STIR, soil_cover and N_input_org on AFE in all maize crops and the real observations (*all_data_maize*, blue line = linear prediction with confidence interval, yellow points = observations with fitted curve, AFE = kg yield dry matter/kg N_input, N and C_input in kg/ha, soil cover in %, STIR see table 3)

C-input-covercrop has no predicted effect on AFE. STIR and soil cover have a slightly positive predicted effect on AFE. Some outliers of the real observations show much higher AFE at different values.

N(C)-input-org shows a clearly negative predicted effect on AFE, which is confirmed by the real observations.

Table 7 shows a summary of these estimated coefficients on *yield / biomass* and on AFE. The R² values say that about 42% of the *yield/biomass* variance can be explained by the independent variables and 58% is explained by the random variables. Only 17% of the AFE in wheat can be explained by the independent variables. In maize 58% can be explained.

Based on these models, hypothesis 1 can be supported as follows:

- Soil-cover has a highly significant positive effect on wheat yield and maize biomass, adding 11.68 kg of dry matter wheat yield and 53.85 kg dry matter maize biomass per percentage point each. It also has a small but positive effect on AFE in maize (plus

0.29 kg yield/kg N input per percentage point each). There is no significant effect of *soil-cover* on AFE in wheat.

The models contradict hypothesis 1 as follows:

- *STIR* has a highly significant positive effect on wheat yield and maize biomass, adding 4.67 kg of dry matter wheat yield and 22.60 kg dry matter maize biomass per *STIR* point. This might be because *STIR* values of the available data are on average very low (mean 54, median < 50). However, figures 7 and 8 suggest, that the impact of more *STIR* points turns negative above a certain value.
There is a positive but small effect of *STIR* on AFE in maize.
- *C-input* from cover-crop and organic amendments (represented by *N-input-org*) has a negative effect on wheat yield and maize biomass. The cover-crop part is very small and not significant. The organic amendment part is a bit clearer and significant.
There is a negative effect of *N-input-org* on AFE in maize.

Table 7 summary linear mixed-effect models yield, biomass and AFE for wheat and maize

		Wheat: yield_DM			Maize: biomass_DM		
		R2m 0.4213169, R2c 0.9984696			R2m 0.4131282, R2c 0.9981149		
Fixed effects	Unit	estimate	p.value	p.star	estimate	p.value	p.star
(Intercept)	kg DM/ha	4'094.06	0.0024	**	8'687.25	0.3375	
C_input_CC	kg / ha	-0.18	0.0971	.	-0.41	0.1732	
STIR (<i>plough=64</i>)	value	4.67	0.0000	***	22.60	0.0000	***
soil_cover	%	11.68	0.0017	**	53.85	0.0006	***
N_input_org	kg / ha	-2.08	0.0442	*	-6.56	0.0553	.
		Wheat: AFE			Maize: AFE		
		R2m 0.1740996, R2c 0.9990414			R2m 0.585892, R2c 0.9989466		
Fixed effects	Unit	estimate	p.value	p.star	estimate	p.value	p.star
(Intercept)	kg DM/ha	131.32	0.0224	*	163.68	0.2728	
C_input_CC	kg / ha	-0.01	0.1292		-0.00	0.3583	
STIR (<i>plough=64</i>)	value	0.06	0.0942	.	0.13	0.0001	***
soil_cover	%	0.08	0.5147		0.29	0.0921	.
N_input_org	kg / ha	-0.63	0.0000	***	-0.49	0.0000	***

4.3 Influence of soil management on climate change resilience

Mean temperatures and precipitation in spring and summer and the determination of their extreme values can be seen in appendix 4. Figure 11 shows their combinations for each LtE location (LtE_name) in spring and summer for the experimental years 1989-2023. The black lines indicate the extreme values. Climatic extreme years are defined here as wet and/or cold years (areas 6,8,9) and as dry and/or warm years (areas 1,2,4). The combinations warm/wet (area 3) and cold/dry (area 7) do not occur.

Figure 11 mean temperatures in °C and precipitation in mm per season for the experimental years 1989 – 2023, black lines indicate the extreme weather, i.e. lower 15% for temperature and precipitation and upper 10% for temperature and upper 15% for precipitation.

In Figure 12 mean relative yields of all LtE treatments are compared between all years (=100%) and the climatic extreme years to find out which treatment copes best in these circumstances. In Chaiblen, mean relative yields are lower in climatic extreme years except of one outlier. For the other LtEs the picture is mirror-like. Burgrain and FAST have higher mean yields in dry/warm years and lower yields in wet/cold years whereby the differences in FAST intensive tilled treatments are much clearer. Oberacker shows the opposite effect, with just small differences in mean relative yield. In appendix 4, the exact values per LtE-treatments are shown, each with the number of observations. Table 8 shows the proportion of climatic extreme years for each LtE.

Table 8 Proportion of climatic extreme years per LtE (total number of trial years)

Proportion of ...	Burgrain (17 years)	Chaiblen (11 years)	FAST (14 years)	Oberacker (28 years)
dry and/or warm years	31%	9%	45%	22%
wet and/or cold years	23%	45%	27%	22%

Chaiblen as the oldest experiment in the coolest and wettest location (see table 4) has only one dry year and almost half of the years are wet and/or cold. FAST as youngest experiment at the warmest location has nearly half of the years warm and/or dry.

FAST treatments with no-tillage (conventional) or reduced tillage (organic) have a smaller reaction of mean relative yield in climatic extreme years. Apart from that, the LtE location itself seems to play a more important role than the treatment in coping with extreme climate. The unspoken assumption that climatic extreme years reduce yield, is only partially confirmed.

Figure 12 mean relative yield per LtE_treatment in climatic extreme years in % of the average over all years (mean relative yield of all years = 100% for each LtE-treatment)

Table 9 summary correlation analyses based on Figures 8, 14 and 15

	Positive correlation			Negative correlation		
	low 0.1-0.3	medium 0.3-0.5	high 0.5-1	low -(0.1-0.3)	medium -(0.3-0.5)	high -(0.5-1)
Yield_DM_wheat all years	Soil_cover, Corg, C_to_clay	C_input_crop	N_input_min Plant_protection			N_input_org
Yield_DM_wheat cold/wet spring	C_input_CC, soil_cover	C_input_crop	N_input_min Plant_protection	STIR		N_input_org
Yield_DM_wheat warm/dry spring	C_org, C_to_clay	C_input_crop, soil_cover, Plant_protection	N_input_min		STIR	N_input_org
Biomass DM maize all years	C_input_CC, soil_cover N_input_min Plant_protection	C_input_crop		STIR N_input_org	Corg	
Biomass DM maize cold/wet summer	C_input_CC, C_to_clay	soil_cover	N_input_min Plant_protection	STIR	N_input_org	
Biomass DM maize warm/dry summer	C_input_crop C_input_CC soil_cover plant_protection	N_input_min		STIR N_input_org C_to_clay		

Table 9 shows a summary of the correlation coefficients $|r| > 0.1$ between management- and soil indicators yield for all wheat data and biomass for all maize data – this in all years and in the years with cold/wet and warm/dry springs and summers. The indicators of interest are highlighted in yellow.

High positive correlations with *N-input-min* and *plant-protection* remain. But in climatic extreme years, *STIR* becomes low to medium negatively correlated to wheat yield. *Soil-cover* becomes positively correlated in warm/dry years with wheat yield, and stronger correlated in cold/wet years with maize biomass. In cold/wet years, cover-crops correlate slightly with wheat yields.

For the linear mixed-effect model analyses, the same model as in chapter 4.2.2 is used with the following difference: The random effect *treatment-ID* is not included, because there are not enough observations for this differentiation for maize crops in warm/dry years. This leads to the following linear mixed-effect model for all-data-wheat in cold/wet and in warm/dry years:

annual_yied_mp_DM * 1000 ~
fixed effects (*C_input_CC* + *STIR* + *soil_cover* + *N_input_org* + *N_input_min* + *plant_protection* + *Corg* + *C_to_clay* + *Prec_spring* + *Temp_spring*) +
random effects (1|*LtE_name/block_ID*) + (1|*LtE_name:year*)

The outcome is shown in appendix 4. In cold/wet years there is no Data for FAST II. In warm/dry years, there is no data for FAST I and Chaiblen. The predicted effects of the four indicators of interest concerning hypothesis 2 are shown in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** – comparing normal years with cold/wet and warm/dry years.

The same model supplemented with the independent variable “crop” is run for all-data-maize in cold/wet and in warm/dry years:

Annual_total_biomass_maincrop_DM * 1000 ~
fixed effects (*C_input_CC* + *STIR* + *soil_cover* + *N_input_org* + *N_input_min* + *plant_protection* + *Corg* + *C_to_clay* + *Prec_spring* + *Temp_spring*) + *crop*
random effects (1|*LtE_name/block_ID*) + (1|*LtE_name:year*)

The outcomes are shown in appendix 4. In cold/wet years there is no data for FAST I. In warm/dry years, there is no data for FAST I and Chaiblen. The predicted effects of the four indicators of interest concerning hypothesis 2 are shown in Figure 14 – comparing normal years with cold/wet and warm/dry years.

Table 10 summary linear mixed effect models wheat yield and maize biomass in climatic extreme years

Wheat, yield_DM,		cold / wet year			warm / dry year		
		R2m 0.440541, R2c 0.9989215			R2m 0.29589, R2c 0.9989138		
Fixed effects	Unit	estimate	p.value	p.star	estimate	p.value	p.star
(Intercept)	kg DM/ha	4'434.18	0.0075	**	3'259.84	0.5061	
<i>C_input_CC</i>	kg / ha	-0.30	0.4465		-0.01	0.9693	
<i>STIR (plough=100)</i>	value	11.22	0.0038	**	-2.76	0.1437	
<i>soil_cover</i>	%	36.23	0.0011	**	-4.97	0.4809	
<i>N_input_org</i>	kg / ha	-3.92	0.3065		-1.20	0.4997	
Maize, biomass_DM		cold / wet year			warm / dry year		
		R2m 0.6380031, R2c 0.9989117			R2m 0.9648353, R2c 0.9648353		
Fixed effects	Unit	estimate	p.value	p.star	estimate	p.value	p.star
(Intercept)	kg DM/ha	36'005.24	0.3706		22'594.07	0.3085	
<i>C_input_CC</i>	kg / ha	-0.67	0.2065		-0.24	0.7866	
<i>STIR (plough=100)</i>	value	46.12	0.0000	***	3.63	0.6814	

soil_cover	%	81.44	0.0033	**	36.01	0.4174
N_input_org	kg / ha	-11.45	0.0809	.	-2.04	0.8641

As shown in Table 10 and figures 13 and 14 in cold/wet years, the effects are similar to all years. For *STIR* and *soil-cover* the positive effects are more pronounced for wheat yield as well as maize biomass. The real observations show a maximum yield at a *STIR* value of about 80 with wheat yields and 150 with maize biomass.

Figure 13 predicted effects of *C_input_CC*, *STIR*, *soil_cover* and *N_input_org* on *annual_yield_mp_DM* wheat in all years and in climatic extreme years and their real observations (*all_data_wheat*, blue line = linear prediction with confidence interval, yellow points = observations with fitted curve)

In warm/dry years, *STIR* and *soil-cover* have a slightly negative effect on wheat yields with the real observations showing a yield maximum at a *STIR* value of 0 and of about 100, and with 65 % *soil-cover*. But these effects are low and not significant.

For the maize biomass in warm/dry years, effects are not clear in the graph. The estimated effects of soil cover and *STIR* remain positive but are not significant.

Figure 14 predicted effects of C_input_CC, STIR, soil_cover and N_input_org on annual_total_biomass_maincrop_DM for maize in all years and in climatic extreme years and their real observations (*all_data_wheat*, blue line = linear prediction with confidence interval, yellow points = observations with fitted curve)

5 Discussion

The discussion focusses on the hypotheses, that lower tillage intensities, more soil cover and higher carbon input lead to higher yields, higher N-use efficiency and less yield loss in climatically extreme years.

5.1 Soil-cover has a positive effect on yield

More soil cover results significantly in higher yields. This effect, which has been shown in LtE Oberacker already (Sturny et al. 2007), is confirmed in the data of all four LtEs and supports the hypothesis. In the concept of regenerative agriculture, consistent soil cover is a key pillar. It requires a suitable crop rotation, and that crop residues, cover crops and organic amendments are systematically left and evenly spread over the soil surface. The resulting permanent layer of mulch which protects soil from drying out, reduces temperature fluctuations, provides nutrients and so promotes soil life (Flury 2020).

A higher tillage intensity results significantly in higher yields too, although it is negatively correlated with soil cover (see appendix 2). This contradicts the hypothesis. Reducing tilling intensity puts high demands on crop management, particularly on weed control. The expected restrictions in plant protection therefore make the scope for action in tillage reduction more difficult. In addition, direct sowing, which does not involve any tillage, does not work for all soils. A sufficiently high earthworm population is essential for successful no-tillage. This only occurs with sufficient rainfall and adequate soil-fauna nutrition (Joschko et al. 2024). There is probably a site-specific optimal range of tillage. Furthermore, way, time and condition of tilling play an important role for soil health and yield building. To understand this more precisely, the STIR value could be differentiated and, for example, combined or weighted with soil conditions (moisture) and season (temperature) at the tilling time.

The effect of carbon input on yield is difficult to interpret. Its subdivision in crop, cover crop and organic amendments makes sense to investigate the effects of soil parameters. With yield parameters to be explained, there are interactions and dependencies to be considered. Carbon input from crop could not be taken into the explaining model because it is calculated as a function of yield. It could make sense to calculate carbon input from crop residues separately, as this variable could be taken into the model and might show an effect. Carbon input from cover crops showed no significant effect on yield. Carbon input from organic amendments showed a slightly significant negative effect on yield. In the available data, organic carbon input occurs mainly in organic treatments, which achieve lower yields due to restrictions on plant protection and fertilization. To overcome this, at least organic treatments would have to be evaluated separately.

Summarized it can be said, that improved soil management improves soil quality, but only increased soil cover also increases yield directly. Reduced tillage is likely to result in lower yield, especially in combination with restricted plant protection (weeds). The impact of more carbon input cannot be judged with the used explanatory models.

5.2 Apparent Fertilizer use Efficiency (AFE) needs more information in the explaining model

The chosen indicator for N-productivity (AFE) is, as all nitrogen use efficiencies in general, a complex term. There are various N sources (fertilizer, SOC, N-fixation) and interactions between

soil N availability, N-transformation, -storage, -movement and N-losses and with soil management and weather. This must be taken into account in the explanatory model, which is not the case in model built in chapter 4.2.2. Fertilizer based N use efficiencies (i.e. AFE) ignore soil N-supplies and N-storage. In soils rich in N, AFE is high with low N-input and decreases with rising N-input. AFE says more about N saturation of the soil than about the plants ability to use available N (Congreves et al. 2021). This can be seen in the available data with highly significant negative effects of N-input organic and mineral on AFE (see Appendix 3). Furthermore, all indicators are calculated from harvest to harvest and associated with the respective crop. With only fertilizer N taken into account, AFE becomes infinite in crop periods without fertilization. Fertilization in advance in the pre crop is not taken into account. Neither are N-fixation and N-stocks. To really make use of AFE as an indicator for productivity, additional indicators, that map the missing information must be taken into the explaining model.

5.3 Warm and/or dry years can result in higher yields

Climatic extreme years do not necessarily lead to lower yields. LtEs of Burgrain and FAST have higher yields in warm and/or dry years, even though both crop rotations include temporary ley, and yields from grassland react with significant losses in drought years (Calanca et al. 2022). Rapeseed has shallower roots than wheat and corn, and potatoes react to soil water shortages and high temperatures with yield losses (Wuyts et al. 2023). Rapeseed and potatoes in the crop rotation of Burgrain, do not lead to lower yield in warm/dry years. It seems that drought and heat are not the limiting factors in yield building in FAST and Burgrain but rather plant disease pressure. This would also explain the lower yields in wet years. Furthermore, in FAST – the youngest and warmest LtE site, almost half of the years are considered warm and or dry. Accordingly, the definition of climatically extreme years needs to be reconsidered. Site specific definitions are necessary to have a more balanced proportion of extreme years at all locations.

5.4 Climatic extreme years need an adapted soil management

In cold and/or wet years, more soil cover and STIR have a significant positive effect in maintaining wheat yield and maize biomass. Their effects are greater than in all year's average. For STIR there seem to be optimal ranges similar to all years data.

In warm/dry years the effect of soil cover and STIR turn slightly negative for wheat yield and remain slightly positive for maize biomass. These effects are only low and not significant. This indicates that climatically extreme years need an adapted soil management and the penalty for no-till is less in dry years. This is confirmed by a global meta-analysis of no-till relative to conventional tillage yields using 678 studies. It found, that no till reduced yields, on average by 5.1% across 50 crops and 6005 paired observations, and that no-till performed best under rainfed conditions in dry climates, matching conventional tillage yield on average. (Pittelkow et al. 2015). It remains unclear to what extend the lacking data of the LtEs Chaiblen and FAST I in warm/dry years and of FAST I+II in cold/wet years causes the differences. For valid modelling, more data is needed, and an adapted definition of climatically extreme years for each LtE individually.

6 Conclusions and outlook

Reduced tillage, more soil cover and more carbon input are the three investigated soil improving management measures. The analyzed data of four LtEs shows that more soil cover has a significant positive effect on yields. This is the case for wheat yield, for maize biomass and for relative yields over all crops. In climatically extreme years the positive effect of soil cover is even more pronounced. The analyzed data shows further, that more tillage up to a crop specific level has a positive effect on yields, and that the penalty of reduced tilling is less or even turns to a reward in warm and/or dry years. The impact of more carbon input could not be assessed using the method applied due to various interactions that are not represented accurately in the model. The assessment of the three soil improving management measures' impact on nitrogen fertilizer use efficiency does not produce any useful results because important information like nitrogen fixation and nitrogen stock in the soil are not included in the explaining model.

The results show, that the conflict of purposes between maximizing yields and sustainable soil- and crop management not only applies to fertilization and plant protection. This conflict is also apparent with tillage intensity. There seems to be an optimal range of tillage intensity for each LtE site, depending on the given pedo-climatic conditions. More soil cover, that serves both purposes, can be increased by less tillage, but also by leaving crop residues on the soil, altering crop rotations, introducing cover crops and applying of organic amendments, which seem to be the more preferable methods, especially in cold and wet conditions.

The chosen approach and the used models are a first attempt using simple means to find out what the processed data of the four LtEs can say about the impact of soil management on yield, productivity and climate change resilience. The results show, that the approach and the explaining models need to be developed to address various weaknesses. The use of just one linear mixed-effect model for the whole data range encounters limitations when describing non-linear effects. Optimal ranges and tipping points of the indicators, adapted to the different pedo-climatic conditions, can't be found. The restrictions in fertilization and plant protection measures of organic treatments have much stronger impact on yield as the soil management measures. The introduced random effect "LtE-treatment" into the linear mixed-model does not sufficiently reflect this effect. Carbon input by crop can't be included into the explaining model. The chosen definition of climatic extreme years leads to an unbalanced representation of the four LtEs in the subsamples. The lack of data in sub samples like climatic extreme years with no data from entire LtEs, eventually influences the result. The attempt to assess N-productivity with the indicator nitrogen fertilizer use efficiency (AFE) falls short, because important variables like nitrogen fixation and nitrogen storage over several crop periods are not considered.

As an outlook, the following tasks could improve the weaknesses of the approach and generate more precise predictions about the impact of the soil management measures:

- Expand data basis with further LtEs,
- Determine optimal ranges and tipping points of the indicators, adapted to the different pedo-climatic conditions with non-linear methods or by working with intervals,
- Evaluate organic treatments separately,
- Focus also on other influencing variables (i.e. lime application), design further management indicators (i.e. carbon input from residues, nitrogen-storage, etc.),
- Measure climate change resilience differently, i.e. with site-specific extreme values, responses to heat waves and heavy rainfalls or other definitions of climatic extreme years,
- Generalize the statements by comparing them with data from practical farms.

Appendix 1 – descriptive analyses

SoilManageR Indicators by the 29 LtE treatments – mean values per year (all_data_per_year)

FAST I + II are very similar. So for a clearer presentation, the graph shows just FAST I

LtE_treatment	C_input	C_i_cr	C_i_cc	C_i_org	STIR	soil_c	N_inp	N_i_o	N_i_m	plant_p	LSU
Burgrain Bio	3'993	2'661	143	1'190	86	84	130	130	-	0.39	1.24
Burgrain IPe	4'116	2'704	97	1'315	66	85	171	139	31	1.82	1.33
Burgrain IPI	4'409	2'824	87	1'498	76	83	213	156	56	2.65	1.49
Chaiblen Getreidebetont IP	2'360	1'999	327	34	118	69	97	4	94	1.27	0.03
Chaiblen Getreidebetont IS	2'565	2'187	327	51	109	69	136	5	130	2.64	0.05
Chaiblen Maisbetont IP	2'474	1'453	208	813	63	64	159	85	74	2.09	0.81
Chaiblen Maisbetont IS	2'411	1'478	-	933	82	59	203	98	105	2.09	0.93
Chaiblen Vielseitig IP	2'956	1'915	145	897	85	75	141	94	48	1.45	0.89
Chaiblen Vielseitig IS	3'248	1'983	145	1'121	83	75	196	117	78	2.09	1.12
FAST I C-IT mixture half	3'069	2'569	500	-	72	80	72	-	72	1.83	-
FAST I C-IT mixture norm	2'961	2'490	470	-	69	80	97	-	97	1.84	-
FAST I C-IT none half	2'530	2'530	-	-	72	69	72	-	72	1.83	-
FAST I C-IT none norm	2'525	2'525	-	-	71	69	96	-	96	1.84	-
FAST I C-NT mixture half	2'939	2'441	498	-	3	91	72	-	72	2.67	-
FAST I C-NT mixture norm	2'831	2'371	460	-	3	90	98	-	98	2.62	-
FAST I C-NT none half	2'452	2'452	-	-	2	77	72	-	72	2.67	-
FAST I C-NT none norm	2'452	2'452	-	-	2	77	96	-	96	2.67	-
FAST I O-IT mixture half	4'197	2'488	500	1'209	81	80	117	117	-	-	1.09
FAST I O-IT mixture norm	4'290	2'504	500	1'286	81	80	137	137	-	-	1.09
FAST I O-IT none half	3'632	2'423	-	1'209	81	68	117	117	-	-	1.09
FAST I O-IT none norm	3'769	2'483	-	1'286	81	69	137	137	-	-	1.09
FAST I O-RT mixture half	4'087	2'379	500	1'209	36	81	117	117	-	-	1.09
FAST I O-RT mixture norm	4'158	2'372	500	1'286	36	81	137	137	-	-	1.09
FAST I O-RT none half	3'475	2'267	-	1'209	36	67	117	117	-	-	1.09
FAST I O-RT none norm	3'604	2'318	-	1'286	36	67	137	137	-	-	1.09
Oberacker No-till GRUD	4'283	2'970	1'247	66	20	94	76	4	72	3.91	0.04
Oberacker No-till Kinsey	4'313	3'000	1'247	66	20	94	76	4	72	3.91	0.04
Oberacker Plough GRUD	4'151	2'855	1'244	52	91	80	73	4	69	3.38	0.03
Oberacker Plough Kinsey	4'128	2'832	1'244	52	91	80	73	4	69	3.38	0.03
mean	3'392	2'411	358	623	60	77	118	64	54	1.69	0.58
standarddeviation	726	367	405	593	33	9	40	62	41	1.27	0.55
min value	2'360	1'453	-	-	2	59	72	-	-	-	-
max value	4'409	3'000	1'247	1'498	118	94	213	156	130	3.91	1.49

Response variable yield and N use efficiency individual values (all_data_per_crop, 2'500 data sets)

AFE = apparent fertilizer efficiency = kg DM yield per kg N_input

NUE = Nitrogen use efficiency = kg N output / kg N_input

Indicator	Annual_yield	Relative_yield	AFE*	NUE*
Mean	8.3 t DM / ha	87 %	82 kg / kg	1.5 kg / kg
Standard deviation	4.6 t DM / ha	26 %	69 kg / kg	1.1 kg / kg

*mean and standard deviation calculated without all the zero N_input values

Response variable mean yield and relative yield by LtE and crop (*all_data_per_crop*)

crop	Mean relative yield in % of GRUD reference					Mean yield in t/ha DM				
	Burgrain	Oberacker	Chaiblen	FAST	mean	Burgrain	Oberacker	Chaiblen	FAST	mean
barley, spring (SG)	0.93	0.47			0.70	4.36	2.18			3.27
barley, winter (WG)	1.12	1.12	1.04		1.09	5.70	5.72	5.32		5.58
beet, sugar (ZR)		0.74			0.74		14.79			14.79
faba bean, spring (AB)		0.66		0.95	0.80		2.25		3.23	2.74
ley, temporary (KW)	1.23		0.81	0.70	0.91	15.97		10.51	9.14	11.87
maize, grain (KM)	0.82			0.98	0.90	6.94			8.34	7.64
maize, silage (SM)	1.06	1.05	0.74		0.95	19.60	19.19	13.64		17.48
oat, spring (SH)		1.13			1.13		5.27			5.27
pea, spring (EE)		0.95		0.79	0.87		3.10		1.32	2.21
pea, winter (EE)		0.76			0.76		2.54			2.54
potato (KA)	1.01	0.91	0.89		0.94	10.01	9.03	8.80		9.28
rapeseed, winter (RA)			0.94		0.94			2.95		2.95
rye, winter (WR)		1.12			1.12		5.25			5.25
soybean (SO)		1.09			1.09		2.93			2.93
wheat, spring (SW)		0.97			0.97		4.12			4.12
wheat, winter (WW)	1.06	0.95	1.03	0.81	0.96	5.42	4.88	5.24	4.12	4.92
mean	1.03	0.92	0.91	0.85	0.93	9.71	6.25	7.74	5.23	6.43

Response variable AFE by LtE and crop (*all_data_per_crop*)

(Apparent Fertilizer use Efficiency = yield in kg dry matter per kg N fertilizer input)

crop	Burgrain	Oberacker	Chaiblen	FAST	average
barley, spring	Inf	15.5			15.5
barley, winter	Inf	75.2	69.4		72.3
beet, sugar		213.1			213.1
faba bean, spring		Inf		Inf	
ley, temporary	91.4		35.8	77.7	68.3
maize, grain	22.0			83.8	52.9
maize, silage	54.7	177.0	120.2		117.3
oat, spring		97.6			97.6
pea, spring		Inf		Inf	
pea, winter		Inf			
potato	40.5	99.3	Inf		69.9
rapeseed, winter			26.0		26.0
rye, winter		Inf			
soybean		Inf			
wheat, spring		Inf			
wheat, winter	Inf	43.3	47.6	38.5	43.1

Inf = no N fertilizer applied

Appendix 2 – correlation analyses

Within the management indicators there are medium positive correlations between *C_input_CC* / *plant_protection* and *N_input_min* / *plant_protection*, and medium negative correlations between *N_input_org* / *plant_protection*, *N_input_org* / *N_input_min* and *STIR* / *soil_cover*. This reflects the characteristics of different treatment concepts.

Correlation matrix for productivity-, management- and soil indicators (all_data_per_crop), 2'500 observations

correlation matrices for productivity-, management- and soil indicators for wheat (l) and maize (r) (all_data_wheat), 613 observations, (all_data_maize), 463 observations

Appendix 3 – linear mixed-effect models for yield, biomass and AFE

Linear mixed-effect model for all_data_wheat and annual_yield_mp_DM.

annual_yied_mp_DM * 1000 ~
fixed effects (C_input_CC + STIR + soil_cover + N_input_org + N_input_min + plant_protection + Corg + C_to_clay + Prec_spring + Temp_spring) +
random effects (1|LtE_name/block_ID/treatment_ID) + (1|LtE_name:year)

AIC:[1] 8915.391, R2m 0.4213169, R2c 0.9984696

Random effects:	Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
	treatment_ID:block_ID:LtE_name	(Intercept)	54863	234.23
	LtE_name:year	(Intercept)	301502	549.09
	block_ID:LtE_name	(Intercept)	34662	186.18
	LtE_name	(Intercept)	422181	649.75
	Residual		2156	46.44

Number of obs: 565, groups: treatment_ID:block_ID:LtE_name, 188; LtE_name:year, 50;
block_ID:LtE_name, 23; LtE_name, 5

Fixed effects	estimate	std.error	statistic	df	p.value	p.star
(Intercept)	4'094.06	1'292.60	3.17	63	0.0024	**
C_input_CC	-0.18	0.11	-1.66	524	0.0971	.
STIR	4.67	1.06	4.41	494	0.0000	***
soil_cover	11.68	3.71	3.15	416	0.0017	**
N_input_org	-2.08	1.03	-2.02	429	0.0442	*
N_input_min	7.69	1.02	7.54	510	0.0000	***
plant_protection	117.93	32.88	3.59	542	0.0004	***
Corg	-83.82	150.11	-0.56	102	0.5778	.
C_to_clay	8.30	42.14	0.20	155	0.8441	.
Prec_spring	-2.05	1.05	-1.95	46	0.0575	.
Temp_spring	-63.73	114.81	-0.56	47	0.5815	.

Linear mixed-effect model for all_data_maize and annual_total_biomass_mp_DM

Annual_total_biomass_maincrop_DM * 1000 ~
fixed effects (C_input_CC + STIR + soil_cover + N_input_org + N_input_min + plant_protection + Corg + C_to_clay + Prec_summer + Temp_summer) +crop
random effects (1|LtE_name/block_ID/treatment_ID) + (1|LtE_name:year)

AIC:[1] 8027.141, R2m 0.4131282, R2c 0.9981149

Random effects:	Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
	treatment_ID:block_ID:LtE_name	(Intercept)	77883	279
	LtE_name:year	(Intercept)	3985636	1996
	block_ID:LtE_name	(Intercept)	71106	267
	LtE_name	(Intercept)	12064868	3474
	Residual		52202	229

Number of obs: 437, groups: treatment_ID:block_ID:LtE_name, 188; LtE_name:year, 50;
block_ID:LtE_name, 23; LtE_name, 5

term	estimate	std.error	statistic	df	p.value	p.star
(Intercept)	8'687.25	8'974.14	0.97	52	0.3375	.
C_input_CC	-0.41	0.30	-1.37	172	0.1732	.
STIR	22.60	3.42	6.61	329	0.0000	***
soil_cover	53.85	15.33	3.51	176	0.0006	***
N_input_org	-6.56	3.41	-1.93	222	0.0553	.
N_input_min	10.64	3.51	3.03	176	0.0028	**
plant_protection	609.05	130.21	4.68	268	0.0000	***
Corg	-953.40	531.79	-1.79	59	0.0782	.
C_to_clay	-53.18	150.23	-0.35	93	0.7242	.
Prec_summer	-6.70	4.96	-1.35	45	0.1835	.
Temp_summer	213.84	409.40	0.52	46	0.6040	.
cropmaize, silage	5'094.35	1'249.26	4.08	42	0.0002	***

Linear mixed-effect model for all_data_wheat and AFE. Datapoints with infinite AFE values are filtered out of the dataset.

AFE ~ fixed effects (C_input_CC + STIR + soil_cover + N_input_org + N_input_min + plant_protection + Corg + C_to_clay + Prec_summer + Temp_summer)
random effects (1|LtE_name/block_ID/treatment_ID) + (1|LtE_name:year)

AIC:[1] 5069.989, R2m 0.1740996, R2c 0.9990414

Random effects:	Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
	treatment_ID:block_ID:LtE_name	(Intercept)	145.00	12.04
	LtE_name:year	(Intercept)	711.30	26.67
	block_ID:LtE_name	(Intercept)	0.00	0.00
	LtE_name	(Intercept)	763.10	27.62
	Residual		1.88	1.37

Number of obs: 558, groups: treatment_ID:block_ID:LtE_name, 187; LtE_name:year, 50; block_ID:LtE_name, 23; LtE_name, 5

term	estimate	std.error	statistic	df	p.value	p.star
(Intercept)	131.32	55.77	2.35	52	0.0224	*
C_input_CC	-0.01	0.00	-1.52	528	0.1292	
STIR	0.06	0.04	1.68	500	0.0942	.
soil_cover	0.08	0.13	0.65	487	0.5147	
N_input_org	-0.63	0.04	-17.93	527	0.0000	***
N_input_min	-0.47	0.03	-13.65	539	0.0000	***
plant_protection	-1.50	1.10	-1.35	524	0.1761	
Corg	-6.66	5.75	-1.16	173	0.2490	
C_to_clay	0.55	1.53	0.36	220	0.7219	
Prec_spring	-0.00	0.05	-0.02	41	0.9830	
Temp_spring	-1.52	5.11	-0.30	42	0.7669	

Linear mixed-effect model for all_data_maize and AFE. Datapoints with infinite AFE values are filtered out of the dataset.

AFE ~ fixed effects (C_input_CC + STIR + soil_cover + N_input_org + N_input_min + plant_protection + Corg + C_to_clay + Prec_spring + Temp_spring + crop)
random effects (1|LtE_name/block_ID/treatment_ID) + (1|LtE_name:year)

AIC:[1] 4125.212, R2m 0.585892, R2c 0.9989466

Random effects:	Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
	treatment_ID:block_ID:LtE_name	(Intercept)	59.87	7.74
	LtE_name:year	(Intercept)	1647.97	40.60
	block_ID:LtE_name	(Intercept)	0.00	0.00
	LtE_name	(Intercept)	0.00	0.00
	Residual		4.36	2.09

Number of obs: 437, groups: treatment_ID:block_ID:LtE_name, 188; LtE_name:year, 50; block_ID:LtE_name, 23; LtE_name, 5

term	estimate	std.error	statistic	df	p.value	p.star
(Intercept)	163.68	147.73	1.11	54	0.2728	
C_input_CC	-0.00	0.00	-0.92	332	0.3583	
STIR	0.13	0.03	3.90	356	0.0001	***
soil_cover	0.29	0.17	1.69	332	0.0921	.
N_input_org	-0.49	0.03	-14.95	319	0.0000	***
N_input_min	-0.39	0.04	-10.28	288	0.0000	***
plant_protection	6.50	1.32	4.91	365	0.0000	***
Corg	-4.24	5.43	-0.78	162	0.4359	
C_to_clay	-0.58	1.55	-0.38	205	0.7065	
Prec_summer	0.01	0.09	0.15	48	0.8808	
Temp_summer	-2.00	6.86	-0.29	50	0.7720	
cropmaize, silage	55.40	14.76	3.75	55	0.0004	***

Appendix 4 – climate data

Climate data 1989 – 2023 per season for all LtE locations (source: Meteoschweiz) and calculation of the extreme values for temperature and precipitation

	temperature				precipitation			
	winter	spring	summer	fall	winter	spring	summer	fall
Minimum	-1.60	6.90	16.40	6.90	102	106	175	90
Maximum	3.50	11.20	21.40	12.10	482	529	603	496
Median	1.30	9.30	17.75	9.35	209	238	343	239
Mean	1.12	9.15	18.03	9.43	219	257	340	250
Standard deviation	1.32	0.93	1.09	1.07	69	88	84	87
lower15%	-0.6	8.1	17.0	8.3	155	177	248	155
upper 10% / 15%	2.7	10.2	19.8	11.0	304	337	400	374

mean relative yield per LtE treatment, all years compared with cold/wet and warm/dry years

(all_data_per_crop, absolute values and in % of all years values, number of observations shown in columns "n")

LtE_treatment	mean relative yield							
	all years	n	cold/wet	in %	n	warm/dry	in %	n
Burgrain_Bio	98.99	78	95.84	97%	18	103.02	104%	24
Burgrain_IPe	103.65	78	102.75	99%	18	109.26	105%	24
Burgrain_IPi	117.93	78	113.50	96%	18	122.10	104%	24
Chaiblen_GIP	87.66	33	80.92	92%	15	72.05	82%	3
Chaiblen_GIS	105.82	33	95.09	90%	15	132.89	126%	3
Chaiblen_MIP	79.62	33	79.04	99%	15	62.07	78%	3
Chaiblen_MIS	86.04	33	80.99	94%	15	72.22	84%	3
Chaiblen_VIP	83.40	33	78.58	94%	15	70.08	84%	3
Chaiblen_VIS	90.47	33	82.42	91%	15	72.38	80%	3
FAST_I_C-IT_mixture_half	98.58	44	86.70	88%	12	113.59	115%	20
FAST_I_C-IT_mixture_norm	104.59	47	96.94	93%	15	117.06	112%	20
FAST_I_C-IT_none_half	96.29	44	84.63	88%	12	107.35	111%	20
FAST_I_C-IT_none_norm	100.84	45	92.02	91%	13	111.47	111%	20
FAST_I_C-NT_mixture_half	89.26	44	88.03	99%	12	93.96	105%	20
FAST_I_C-NT_mixture_norm	93.78	48	90.69	97%	16	97.11	104%	20
FAST_I_C-NT_none_half	89.54	44	87.07	97%	12	95.00	106%	20
FAST_I_C-NT_none_norm	91.44	44	88.09	96%	12	94.32	103%	20
FAST_I_O-IT_mixture_half	84.25	44	60.63	72%	12	103.82	123%	20
FAST_I_O-IT_mixture_norm	86.51	44	69.45	80%	12	107.16	124%	20
FAST_I_O-IT_none_half	80.40	44	62.77	78%	12	94.10	117%	20
FAST_I_O-IT_none_norm	88.86	44	73.49	83%	12	105.32	119%	20
FAST_I_O-RT_mixture_half	76.32	44	61.08	80%	12	87.87	115%	20
FAST_I_O-RT_mixture_norm	80.28	44	79.39	99%	12	90.96	113%	20
FAST_I_O-RT_none_half	69.88	44	56.90	81%	12	75.00	107%	20
FAST_I_O-RT_none_norm	74.04	44	70.31	95%	12	81.27	110%	20
Oberacker_No-till_GRUD	93.64	163	96.44	103%	36	90.51	97%	36
Oberacker_No-till_Kinsey	94.78	163	98.66	104%	36	92.40	97%	36
Oberacker_Plough_GRUD	90.87	163	91.85	101%	36	92.76	102%	36
Oberacker_Plough_Kinsey	90.90	163	95.07	105%	36	89.44	98%	36

Linear mixed-effect model - all_data_wheat_cold/wet

annual_yied_mp_DM * 1000 ~
fixed effects (C_input_CC + STIR + soil_cover + N_input_org + N_input_min +
 plant_protection + Corg + C_to_clay + Prec_spring + Temp_spring) +
random effects (1|LtE_name/block_ID) + (1|LtE_name:year)

AIC:[1] 1519.035, R2m 0.440541, R2c 0.9989215

Random effects:	Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
	block_ID:LtE_name	(Intercept)	119639	346
	LtE_name:year	(Intercept)	0	0
	LtE_name	(Intercept)	888134	942
	Residual		1947	44

Number of obs: 101, groups: LtE_name:year, 15;block_ID:LtE_name, 11, LtE_name, 4, (no values for FAST_II)

Fixed effects	estimate	std.error	statistic	df	p.value	p.star
(Intercept)	4'434.18	1'607.22	2.76	65	0.0075	**
C_input_CC	-0.30	0.39	-0.77	75	0.4465	
STIR	11.22	3.77	2.98	84	0.0038	**
soil_cover	36.23	10.73	3.38	83	0.0011	**
N_input_org	-3.92	3.81	-1.03	88	0.3065	
N_input_min	5.63	2.71	2.07	89	0.0409	*
plant_protection	196.71	71.16	2.76	89	0.0069	**
Corg	-562.00	205.16	-2.74	89	0.0074	**
C_to_clay	-9.46	89.54	-0.11	89	0.9161	
Prec_spring	-1.58	1.52	-1.04	29	0.3080	
Temp_spring	-253.66	162.32	-1.56	53	0.1240	

Linear mixed-effect model - all_data_wheat_warm/dry

annual_yied_mp_DM * 1000 ~
fixed effects (C_input_CC + STIR + soil_cover + N_input_org + N_input_min +
 plant_protection + Corg + C_to_clay + Prec_spring + Temp_spring) +
random effects (1|LtE_name/block_ID) + (1|LtE_name:year)

AIC:[1] 2494.503, R2m 0.29589, R2c 0.9989138

Random effects:	Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
	LtE_name:year	(Intercept)	62343	250
	block_ID:LtE_name	(Intercept)	422164	650
	LtE_name	(Intercept)	1121777	1059
	Residual		2521	50

Number of obs: 160, groups: LtE_name:year, 12;block_ID:LtE_name, 10; LtE_name, 3 (no values for Chaiblen and FAST I)

Fixed effects	estimate	std.error	statistic	df	p.value	p.star
(Intercept)	3'259.84	4'731.55	0.69	10	0.5061	
C_input_CC	-0.01	0.18	-0.04	147	0.9693	
STIR	-2.76	1.88	-1.47	143	0.1437	
soil_cover	-4.97	7.03	-0.71	144	0.4809	
N_input_org	-1.20	1.77	-0.68	144	0.4997	
N_input_min	14.73	1.79	8.25	146	0.0000	***
plant_protection	-109.56	72.96	-1.50	146	0.1353	
Corg	367.55	411.19	0.89	118	0.3732	
C_to_clay	56.59	65.50	0.86	139	0.3891	
Prec_spring	-3.70	4.66	-0.79	9	0.4489	
Temp_spring	86.66	488.66	0.18	9	0.8630	

Linear mixed-effect model - all_data_maize_cold/wet

annual_total_biomass_maincrop_DM * 1000 ~
fixed effects (C_input_CC + STIR + soil_cover + N_input_org + N_input_min + plant_protection + Corg + C_to_clay + Prec_summer + Temp_summer + crop) +
random effects (1|LtE_name/block_ID) + (1|LtE_name:year)

AIC:[1] 1924.383, R2m 0.6380031, R2c .0. 9989117

Random effects:	Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
	LtE_name:year	(Intercept)	10520000	3243
	block_ID:LtE_name	(Intercept)	0.0	0.0
	LtE_name	(Intercept)	0.0	0.1
	Residual		31710	178

Number of obs: 112, groups: ;block_ID:LtE_name,12; LtE_name:year; 10, LtE_name, 4 (no values for FAST I)

Fixed effects	estimate	std.error	statistic	df	p.value	p.star
(Intercept)	36'005.24	37'355.14	0.96	6	0.3706	
C_input_CC	-0.67	0.53	-1.27	78	0.2065	
STIR	46.12	5.61	8.22	99	0.0000	***
soil_cover	81.44	26.88	3.03	77	0.0033	**
N_input_org	-11.45	6.48	-1.77	80	0.0809	.
N_input_min	24.65	6.74	3.66	100	0.0004	***
plant_protection	1'033.57	255.04	4.05	94	0.0001	***
Corg	-1'098.57	597.46	-1.84	100	0.0689	
C_to_clay	280.39	201.27	1.39	100	0.1667	
Prec_spring	26.68	15.02	1.78	6	0.1249	
Temp_spring	-2'745.60	2'277.99	-1.21	6	0.2727	
Cropmaize, silage	1'722.29	3'349.56	0.51	7	0.6238	

Linear mixed-effect model - all_data_maize_warm/dry

annual_total_biomass_maincrop_DM * 1000 ~
fixed effects (C_input_CC + STIR + soil_cover + N_input_org + N_input_min + plant_protection + Corg + C_to_clay + Prec_summer + Temp_summer + crop) +
random effects (1|LtE_name/block_ID) + (1|LtE_name:year)

AIC:[1] 1387.041, R2m 0.9648353, R2c .0. 9648353

Random effects:	Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
	LtE_name:year	(Intercept)	0.0	0.0
	block_ID:LtE_name	(Intercept)	0.0	0.0
	LtE_name	(Intercept)	0.0	0.2
	Residual		78070	279

Number of obs: 79, groups: ;block_ID:LtE_name, 9; LtE_name:year; 6, LtE_name, 3 (no values for Chaiblen and FAST I)

Fixed effects	estimate	std.error	statistic	df	p.value	p.star
(Intercept)	22'594.07	22'019.83	1.03	67	0.3085	
C_input_CC	-0.24	0.88	-0.27	67	0.7866	
STIR	3.63	8.80	0.41	67	0.6814	
soil_cover	36.01	44.14	0.82	67	0.4174	
N_input_org	-2.04	11.88	-0.17	67	0.8641	
N_input_min	24.03	15.76	1.53	67	0.1320	
plant_protection	-74.27	595.56	-0.12	67	0.9011	
Corg	1'739.93	2'765.48	0.63	67	0.5314	
C_to_clay	-706.64	432.43	-1.63	67	0.1069	
Prec_spring	52.08	61.85	0.84	67	0.4027	
Temp_spring	-836.64	1'024.21	-0.82	67	0.4169	
Cropmaize, silage						

List of abbreviations

CAS	Certificate of Advanced Studies
FHNW	Fachhochschule (University of applied science) Nordwestschweiz
FAT	Forschungsanstalt für Agrarwirtschaft und Landtechnik (today Agroscope)
FAL	Forschungsanstalt für Agrarökologie und Landbau (today Agroscope)
ETH	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule, Zürich
MAS – UM	Master of advanced science in environmental technology and management
LtE	Longterm field experiment
CR	Crop rotation
GRUD	Grundlagen der Düngung der Agroscope, Schweiz
Kinsey	Fertilization recommendation Kinsey Agricultural Service USA

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List of used AI – tools

Tool	Used for ...	Used where ...
DeepL Translate	Translating technical terms and Figures of speech	Entire work
Chat GPT	Understanding and creating R code Explaining technical terms	Data analyses in chapter 3 and 4 Entire work
Perplexity	Understanding and creating R code Explaining technical terms	Data analyses in chapter 3 and 4 Entire work

References

- Agroscope (2025). Klimarisiken Landwirtschaft - Anpassungsmöglichkeiten. URL: <https://www.agroscope.admin.ch/agroscope/de/home/themen/umwelt-ressourcen/klima-lufthygiene/landwirtschaft-im-klimawandel.html>
- Anken, Thomas/Weisskopf, Peter/Zihlmann, Urs/Forrer, Hansrudolf/Jansa, Jan/Perhacova, Katarina (2004). Long-term tillage system effects under moist cool conditions in Switzerland. In: Soil and Tillage Research. 78(2). Jg. S. 171–183. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2004.02.005>.
- BAFU (2024). Grundwasser-Qualität. BAFU. URL: <https://www.bafu.admin.ch/bafu/de/home/themen/wasser/grundwasser/grundwasser-qualitaet.html> [Zugriffsdatum: 01. September 2025].
- Calanca, Pierluigi/Wüest-Galley, Chloé/Giuliani, Silvano/Erudin, Daniel (2022). Auswirkungen der Trockenheit auf die Produktivität des Schweizer Grünlands. In: Agrarforschung Schweiz. 13. Jg. S. 135–144. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34776/afs13-135>.
- Congreves, Kate A./Otchere, Olivia/Ferland, Daphnée/Faradzfar, Soudeh/Williams, Shanay/Arcand, Melissa (2021). Nitrogen use efficiency definitions of today and tomorrow. In: Frontiers plant science. 12–2021. Jg. S. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2021.637108>.
- DATAtab Team (2025). DATAtab: Online Statistics Calculator. URL: <https://datatab.de> [Zugriffsdatum: 01. Juli 2025].
- Flury, Dominique (2020). Was ist Konservierende Landwirtschaft. In: UFA Revue. URL: <https://www.ufarevue.ch/pflanzenbau/was-ist-konservierende-landwirtschaft>
- Förderer, Grischa (2025). Impact of soil- and cropmanagement on soil quality.
- Heller, Olivier/Chervet, Andreas/Durand-Maniclas, Fabien/Guillaume, Thomas/Häfner, Franziska/Müller, Michael/Wittwer, Raphaël/Keller, Thomas (2025). SOILMANAGER —An R Package for Deriving Soil Management Indicators to Harmonise Agricultural Practice Assessments. In: European Journal of Soil Science. 76. Jg. (2). S. e70102. DOI: [10.1111/ejss.70102](https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.70102).
- Heller, Olivier/Wittwer, Raphaël (2025). Pprocessed data of the LtEs Oberacker, FAST, Burgrain, Chaiblen.
- Hemmerich, W (2021). StatistikGuru: AIC, Akaike-Informationskriterium. URL: <https://statistikguru.de/lexikon/aic-akaike-informationskriterium.html> abgerufen
- Hermle, Sandra/Anken, Thomas/Leifeld, Jens/Weisskopf, Peter (2008). The effect of the tillage system on soil organic carbon content under moist, cold-temperature conditions. In: Soil and Tillage Research. 98. Jg. (1). S. 94–105. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2007.10.010>.
- Johannes, Alice/Matter, Adrien/Schulin, Rainer/Weisskopf, Peter/Baveye, Philippe C./Boivin, Pascal (2017). Optimal organic carbon values for soil structure quality of arable soils. Does clay content matter? In: Geoderma. Volume 302. Jg. S. 14–21. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2017.04.021>.
- Joschko, Monika/Harrach, Tamas/Illerhaus, Bernhard/Fritsch, Guido/Hildebrandt, Thomas B/Barkusky, Dietmar/Epperlein, Jana/Senger, Marion/Schulze, Martin/Muckwar, Andreas/Keil, Bernhard/Kuka, Katrin/Gerlach, Felix/Meinel, Dietmar/Schurig, Michael/Szallies, Isabell (2024). Ein Gefügeatlas, Computertomographie von Ackerböden zur Beurteilung des Bodengefüges. Gründung: Verlag Dr. Friedrich Pfeil.
- Jossi, Werner (2000). collected documentation on the longterm field experiment Chaiblen.

Jossi, Werner/Zihlmann, Urs/Valenta, Anna/Scherrer, Caroline/Krebs, Heinz/Dubois, David/Fried, Padrout M./Malitius, Oliver/Anken, Thomas/Sidler, August/Bergmann, Fritz (2002). Vielseitige Fruchtfolge fördert die Ertragsfähigkeit. In: Agrarforschung. 9 (3) 2002. Jg. S. 90–95.

Keller (2024). Statistik und Beratung. URL: <https://statistik-und-beratung.de/2024/09/was-sind-gemischte-modelle-und-wozu-braucht-man-sie/>

Kiener, Bettina (2024). Um die Bodendaten besser zu nutzen. In: Schweizer Bauer. S. 19.

Krause, Hans-Martin/Mäder, Paul/Fliessbach, Andreas/Jarosch, Klaus A./Oberson, Astrid/Mayer, Jochen (2024). Organic cropping systems balance environmental impacts and agricultural production. In: Scientific reports. 14(1). Jg. (25537). S. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-024-76776-1.

Liniger, Hanspeter/Askrabic, Jovana (2024). Warum Böden vor Hitze zu schützen sind. In: UFA Revue. URL: <https://www.ufarevue.ch/pflanzenbau/warum-boeden-vor-hitze-zu-schuetzen-sind>

Maestrini, Luca/Hui, Francis K.C./Welsh, Alan H. (2024). Restricted maximum likelihood estimation in generalized linear mixed models. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2402.12719> [Zugriffsdatum: 01. September 2025].

Möhring, Anke/Drobnik, Thomas/Mack, Gabriele/Amman, Jeanine/El Benni, Nadja (2021). Naturalertragseinbussen durch Verzicht auf Pflanzenschutzmittel im Ackerbau: Resultate einer Delphi-Studie. In: Agroscope Science. 125. Jg. S. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34776/as125g>.

Pittelkow, Cameron M./Linguist, Bruce A./Lundy, Mark E./Liang, Xinqiang/von Groenigen, Kees Jan/Lee, Juhwan/van Gestel, Natasja/Six, Johan/Venterea, Rodney T./van Kessel, Chris (2015). When does no-till yield more? A global meta-analysis. In: Field Crops Research. 183. Jg. S. 156–168. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2015.07.020>.

Sinaj, Sokrat/Charles, Raphaël/Baux, Alice/Dupuis, Brice/Hiltbrunner, Jürg/Levy, Lilia/Pellet, Didier/Blanchet, Guillaume/Jeangros, Bernard (2017). Düngung von Ackerkulturen. In: Agrarforschung Schweiz. 8 (6) Spezialpublikation. Jg. S. URL: https://www.agrarforschungschweiz.ch/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/2017_06_2301.pdf

Sturny, Wolfgang/Chervet, Andreas/Maurer-Troxler, Claudia/Ramseier, Lorenz/Müller, Moritz/Schafflützel, Roland/Richner, Walter/Streit, Bernhard/Weisskopf, Peter/Zihlmann, Urs (2007). Direktsaat und Pflug im Systemvergleich - eine Synthese. In: Agrarforschung. 14 (8). Jg. S. 350–357.

Wagg, Cameron/Schlaeppli, Klaus/Banerjee, Samiran/Kuramae, Eiko E./Van der Heijden, Marcel (2024). Fungal-bacterial diversity and microbiome complexity predict ecosystem functioning. In: Nat Commun. 2019. Jg. S. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-019-12798-y.

Weber, Daniela/Keller, Daniela (2023). Statistische Daten ergeben und auswerten für dummies. Weinheim D: Wiley-VCH GmbH.

Weisskopf, Peter (1986). Erhaltung der Ertragsfähigkeit des Bodens auf lange Sicht unter dem Einfluss von Fruchtfolge, Düngung und Herbizideinsatz. ETH Zürich. Zürich. URL: <https://www.research-collection.ethz.ch/entities/publication/886eb3d3-8662-4e8f-a8de-564dde2452a2> [Zugriffsdatum: 01. Januar 2025].

Wuyts, Nathalie/Baux, Alice/Bragazza, Luca/Calanca, Pierluigi/Chalhoub, Boulos/Dupuis, Brice/Herrera, Juan/Hiltbrunner, Jürg/Levy Häner, Lilia/Pellet, Didier/Toschini, Thomas/Carlen, Christoph (2023). Klimaresilienter Ackerbau 2035. In: Agroscope Science. Nr. 177. Jg. S. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34776/as177g>.